

1 **HMCES and DNMT silencing in early embryonic development in humans.**

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6 DNMT3A and DNMT3B expression are silenced together with HMCES and this occurs concomitant with
7 GADD45A/B induction in early embryonic development in humans. HMCES silencing concomitant with
8 DNMT3A and DNMT3B silencing between the 1st and 3rd cell divisions (1-cell to 8-cell embryo) occurred
9 in a developmentally programmed fashion together with an expression switch involving switching from
10 Tet3 to Tet1/2 expression.

11 Citations

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